

MARKETING PERFORMANCE MODEL THROUGH DIGITAL MARKETING STRATEGY: EMPIRICAL STUDY OF PEGADAIAN DIGITAL SERVICE AT PT. PEGADAIAN

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Abstract

This study is intended to answer and analyze the occurrence of research gaps from various previous research results and also does not rule out the existence of a phenomenon when Management Innovation functions as an inconsistent intervening variable that can explain Marketing Performance. Things like that are the considerations for conducting this study. This type of research is quantitative descriptive with the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis method on the LISREL application. The research objects used are PT Pegadaian Head Office and Jakarta office employees with a population of 758 employees and the number of research samples obtained is 378 employees. The results of this study can be explained that all exogenous variables in this study can explain their influence significantly and are positively correlated with endogenous variables. These results are expected to help management in organizing and maximizing marketing performance through management innovation.

Keywords: Market Oriented Organizational Culture, Organizational Capabilities, Management Innovation, Digital Marketing Strategy, Marketing Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

In Lee, Yoon, Kim, Kang (2017) it is stated that market-oriented culture not only directly affects company performance, but also indirectly by influencing the marketing strategy making process. Meanwhile, Frans Sudirjo (2022) states that market orientation, organizational culture, and entrepreneurial orientation together affect marketing performance. Market orientation has a partial effect on marketing performance. Organizational culture does not have a partial effect on marketing performance. Entrepreneurial orientation has a partial effect on marketing performance. Based on the description of the theory, the low marketing performance of PT Pegadaian is thought to be caused by the relatively low market-oriented organizational culture. This is because market-oriented culture is key to understanding consumer needs and preferences, especially amidst the rapid development of digitalization.

Market-oriented organizational culture grows from the market orientation possessed by all people in the company. The idea of market orientation was first put forward by Kohli and Jaworski (1990). In their qualitative research which was later widely quoted by other researchers regarding market orientation, Kohli and Jaworski (1990) showed the importance of market orientation as a marketing concept and not just as a business philosophy. By synthesizing the existing marketing literature on this issue, and supplementing it with a series of interviews with managers from various levels and functions in several organizations, they were able to derive an operational definition and reliable measurement of the market orientation

variable construct. They argued that market orientation consists of three components: First, the creation of marketing intelligence that captures the dynamics of changing consumer needs and the nature of competition in the marketplace. Second is the dissemination of marketing intelligence to every level and functional area within an organization so that the organization can adapt and be ready to meet market needs. Third is the extent to which internal responses to the marketing intelligence that has been created and disseminated within the organization.

However, Narver et al. (1998) and Homburg and Pflesser (2000) agree with the argument that the conception and measurement of market orientation is better viewed from a cultural perspective rather than a behavioral perspective as suggested by Kohli et al. (1993). The cultural approach to market orientation is considered to be more in-depth in its analysis because it incorporates three different layers of culture, namely underlying basic assumptions, espoused values, and artifacts into its measurement instrument. They also introduce the concept of market-oriented organizational culture, namely the core values of market orientation shared across the organization, organizational norms for market orientation, observable market-oriented artifacts, and market-oriented behaviors. They also highlight the relationship between the three layers of market-oriented organizational culture and organizational performance outcomes, namely financial and market performance subject to the moderating effect of market dynamism. Several studies have highlighted the relationship between market-oriented culture and firm performance (Olavarrieta, 1999, Kasper, 2005), and also a synergistic approach between market-oriented culture and the process and implementation of corporate strategy making also leads to better marketing performance (Yoon, 2005). Organizational culture is necessary for the successful implementation of market-oriented strategies because organizations with market-oriented cultures perform better than other organizations (Byrne, 2018). The role of organizational capabilities in driving the performance of market-oriented organizations has been highlighted many times in the literature. An influential study conducted by Day (1994) showed that a company's capabilities determine its strategy. Capabilities themselves are defined as complex collective skills and learning, deployed through organizational processes, that ensure the superior harmonization of functional activities within an organization. Day (1994) highlighted two key capabilities possessed by market-driven organizations, namely market sensing and customer relationships. Market sensing capability refers to the extent to which an organization can continuously sense changes in market and consumer dynamics. Meanwhile, customer connection capability refers to the skills and abilities to combine collaborative customer relationships across functional areas within an organization. The results of this study not only provide a major contribution to the field of market-oriented organizational culture but have also been useful for managers in determining the actions of an organization's change program to become more market-oriented. Managers must first diagnose current capabilities and anticipated future skills and abilities, then engage in bottom-up business process redesign and top-down direction from senior managers and executive officers, and then utilize the use of Information and Communication Technology to monitor progress. Management innovation is needed to create effective and efficient strategies in taking advantage of opportunities in the digital era. According to Richard M. Walker, Fariborz Damanpour, Carlos A. Devece (2015) stated that the impact of management

innovation on company performance is not direct; but the impact is mediated by management performance. Other results found that management performance has a positive impact on company performance. Meanwhile, Song Guo Jiang (2023) stated that management innovation and organizational inertia affect company performance, and organizational learning has a mediating role. Agus Purwanto, John Tampil Purba, Innocentius Bernarto, Rosdiana Sijabat (2021) stated that knowledge sharing does not have a significant effect on the marketing performance of consumer goods companies. Management innovation does not have a significant effect on the marketing performance of consumer goods companies.

The description above is reinforced by the results of the study by Birkinshaw (2008) which has provided information to managers about the reasons and antecedents of how management innovation occurs in an organization. Birkinshaw (2008) defines management innovation as the design and implementation of management practices, processes, structures, or techniques that are new and aimed at achieving organizational goals. Birkinshaw (2008) shows that there are four perspectives on management innovation, namely the institutional perspective, the fashion perspective, the cultural perspective, and the rational perspective. This perspective shapes how internal change agents initiate the re-creation of new business processes and systems throughout the organization. The mechanism that leads to management innovation involves the interaction of four main determinants, namely starting from the actions of internal change agents in defining new problems to theorizing a new practice, then the actions of external change agents who formulate new practices suggested from the theory. analysis of the business environment, opportunities, and threats. Finally, the organizational and environmental contexts shape four phases in management innovation, namely motivation, discovery, implementation, and theory of new management practices. Mol and Birkinshaw (2009) also agree that management innovation is a consequence of the internal context of the company and the external search for new knowledge. The success of the management innovation process is a good example of how innovation and capabilities are harmoniously interconnected in an organization that is likely to contribute to superior company performance.

The results of research conducted by Williams Kwasi Peparah, et.al., (2017), state that culture has a major influence on global marketing strategies such as promotion strategies, product design, branding, pricing, and distribution processes as well as organizational performance. Therefore, it is important for international marketing managers to pay great attention to the cultural characteristics of local consumers in their marketing strategies. In Indra Muis (2020), that market orientation has a significant influence on export marketing strategy, export marketing capability, and export marketing performance. Then, export marketing strategy significantly affects export marketing performance. In addition, export marketing capability also has a significant influence on export marketing performance. Finally, export marketing strategy and capability play a role in the relationship between market orientation and export performance. By Charles Lagat and Gary L. Frankwick (2017), that the effectiveness of marketing strategy implementation positively moderates the effect of marketing capability on market performance and financial performance of small companies.

By Lucas Jorge Garcia, et. al., (2023) in his research resulted that to identify innovations in marketing used by companies and institutions, mainly consisting of improving the characteristics of the four pillars of marketing (product, price, place and promotion) and improving organizational performance through investigation of internal and external customer experiences, which aims to diversify services and products in the market as a way to attract target audiences and ensure competitive advantage. In the research results of Adijati Utaminingsih (2016), Wahyono (2017), Siti Nurjanah (2014), Muhammad Arif (2011), Satya Devara (2017), Rini Dwiastuti (2012), Sri Harini, et.al., that market orientation, innovation, and creativity of marketing strategies have a significant effect on marketing performance.

II. HYPOTHESIS

H₁: There is an influence of Market Oriented Organizational Culture on Digital Marketing Strategy

H₂: There is an influence of Organizational Capabilities on Digital Marketing Strategy

H₃: There is an influence of Management Innovation on Digital Marketing Strategy

H₄: There is an influence of Market Oriented Organizational Culture on Marketing performance

H₅: There is an influence of Organizational Capabilities on Marketing Performance

H₆: There is an influence of Management Innovation on Marketing Performance

H₇: There is an influence of Digital Marketing Strategy on Marketing Performance

BOBP = Market Oriented Organizational Culture
 KO = Organizational Capabilities
 IM = Management Innovation
 SPD = Digital Marketing Strategy
 KP = Marketing Performance

Figure 1: Research Framework Model

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a descriptive study using a quantitative approach to hypothesis testing with the object of the study being employees of the head office of PT Pegadaian and Jakarta Regions 1 and 2.

The number of employees referred to above as the population is 758 employees. Furthermore, the researcher used a sampling technique by means of proportional random sampling, the determination of sample members by the researcher took representatives from each group in the population whose number was adjusted to the number of subject members in each group, to determine the minimum sample needed if the population is known, the Slovin formula can be used with the assumption that the level of sampling error tolerated is 5% (Sugiono, 2016):

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = population size of 758

e = sampling error rate, which is 5%.

The results of the sample size calculation are as follows:

$$n = \frac{758}{1 + 758 (0,05)^2}$$

$$n = 378$$

Operational Variables:

Table 1: Operational Variables

Section	Variables	Description Indicators	Sources
Part 1	Market Oriented Organizational Culture (X1)	- Core market orientation values shared across the organization.	Narver et al. (1998) and Homburg and Pflesser (2000)
		- Organizational norms for market orientation.	
		- Visible artifacts of market orientation, and market-oriented behaviors.	
Part 2	Organizational Capabilities (X2)	- Market capability refers to the extent to which an organization can continuously sense changes in market and consumer dynamics, including sensing capabilities for directional change (e.g., opportunity identification capabilities, adaptability).	Day (1994), and Lin et al. (2016)
		- Customer linking capabilities refer to the skills and abilities to integrate collaborative customer relationships across functional areas within the organization, including relational capabilities for relationships and social capital acquisition (e.g., social capital integration capabilities, social relationship integration capabilities, interaction	

Section	Variables	Description Indicators	Sources
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fostering capabilities). - Absorptive capacity for organizational learning (e.g., knowledge acquisition, assimilation, transformation, and exploitation capabilities). - Integrative capabilities for communication and coordination (e.g., resource reallocation and reconfiguration capabilities, knowledge integration capabilities) 	
Part 3	Management Innovation (X3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The extent to which the design and implementation of new management practices, processes, structures, or techniques - The extent to which the actions of internal change agents interact in defining new problems to new practices - The extent to which the actions of external change agents formulate new theoretical practices suggested from the analysis of the business environment, opportunities, and threats - The organizational and environmental contexts shape the four phases of management innovation, namely motivation, discovery, implementation, and theory of new management practices. 	Birkinshaw (2008), and Lin et al. (2016)
Part 4	Digital Marketing Strategy (Y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To what extent the company's organizational architecture must be in accordance with its business strategy (digital marketing strategy), namely marketing structure, policies, procedures, and programs (strategy formulation stage) - To what extent is control needed and flexibility needed in an organization regarding the four types of culture, namely adhocracy, market, clan, and hierarchy (strategy implementation stage) - To what extent is the adaptive process enabled by technology where companies work together with customers and partners to mutually create, communicate, deliver, and maintain value for all stakeholders 	Slater et al. (2011) Kannan and Li (2017)
Part 5	Marketing Performance (Z)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Market performance depends on the dynamics of the competitive environment around the organization - Market performance is subject to satisfying the ever-changing needs and behavior of customers by using market intelligence to continuously assess the dynamics of consumer needs and behavior. - Market performance depends on the creation of superior brand equity and performance - Percentage of market share achieved - Assessment of customer satisfaction, customer loyalty, customer equity, and customer lifetime value 	Deshpandé and Farley (1998) Rossiter (2012) Iyer et al. (2020) The Indonesian Financial Service Authority, and internal data.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Analysis of Research Variable Description

Table 2: Score Range and Categories

Score Interval	Market-Oriented Organizational Culture	Organizational Capabilities	Management Innovation	Digital Marketing Strategy	Marketing Performance
1,00-1,80	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
1,81-2,60	Very Low	Very Low	Very Low	Very Low	Very Low
2,61-3,40	Quite High	Quite High	Quite High	Quite High	Quite High
3,41-4,20	High	High	High	High	High
4,21-5,00	Very High	Very High	Very High	Very High	Very High

Source: Zikmund, William G., et. al (2019)

Table 3: Market-Oriented Organizational Culture of Management Level Employees at PT Pegadaian in DKI Jakarta (n=378)

Market-Oriented Organizational Culture Indicator (BOBP)		Score	Average	Category
Customer Satisfaction (X1)				
BOBP1	Appreciating employees..	1278	3.38	High Enough
BOBP2	Speed in work processes.	1414	3.74	High
BOBP3	Creativity and flexibility in serving customers	1410	3.73	High
Average Customer Satisfaction (X1)		1367.33	3.62	High
Customer Loyalty (X2)				
BOBP4	Appreciation to customers.	1307	3.46	High
BOBP5	Researching customer issues.	1158	3.06	High Enough
BOBP6	Comfort of customer waiting room	1480	3.92	High
Average Customer Loyalty (X2)		1315.00	3.48	High
Sustainable competitive advantage (X3)				
BOBP7	Measuring and managing market performance.	1383	3.66	High
BOBP8	Value-added and competitive products and services.	1277	3.38	High Enough
Average Sustainable Competitive Advantage (X3)		1330.00	3.52	High
Average Market Oriented Organizational Culture		1337.44	3.54	High

Source: Processed data

Table 4: Organizational Capabilities of Management Level Employees at PT Pegadaian in DKI Jakarta (n=378)

Organizational Capability Indicator (OC)		Score	Average	Category
Human resources (X4)				
KO1	HR has skills and abilities	1410	3.73	High
KO2	Adaptability	1480	3.92	High
KO3	Relational ability	1383	3.66	High
Average Human Resources (X4)		1424.33	3.77	High
Technology (X5)				
KO4	Have analytical tools for market shifts and changes.	1420	3.76	High
KO5	Quickly respond to the dynamics of customer needs.	1458	3.86	High
Average Technology (X5)		1439.00	3.81	High
Process (X6)				

Organizational Capability Indicator (OC)		Score	Average	Category
KO6	Efficient business process.	1475	3.90	High
KO7	Able to create customer needs quickly.	1426	3.77	High
KO8	Absorption of new knowledge to promote products.	1361	3.60	High
Process Average (X6)		1420.67	3.76	High
Average Organizational Capabilities		1428.00	3.78	High

Source: Processed data

Table 5: Management Innovation in Management Level Employees at PT Pegadaian in DKI Jakarta (n=378)

Management Innovation Indicator (IM)		Score	Average	Category
Working Method (X7)				
IM1	Able to identify problems	1192	3.15	High Enough
IM2	Create product proposals with new services	1318	3.49	High
IM3	Innovation is supported by all elements of the organization	1397	3.70	High
Average Working Method (X7)		1302.33	3.45	High
Leadership Approach (X8)				
IM4	Have a great concern to update management practices	1388	3.67	High
IM5	The right management practice approach to face competitors	1514	4.01	High
IM6	Implement management practices in business activities	1539	4.07	High
Average Leadership Approach (X8)		1480.33	3.92	High
Average Management Innovation		1391.33	3.68	High

Source: Processed data

Table 6: Digital Marketing Strategy for Management Level Employees of PT Pegadaian in DKI Jakarta (n=378)

Digital Marketing Strategy Indicators (DST)		Score	Average	Category
Promoting products or services (Y1)				
SPD1	Developing digital platforms and services	1452	3.84	High
SPD2	Developing platforms through digital marketing campaigns	1449	3.83	High
SPD3	Promoting and managing platforms on social media	1375	3.64	High
Average Promoting a product or service (Y1)		1425.33	3.77	High
Building a brand (Y2)				
SPD4	Customer brand recognition ability	1348	3.57	High
SPD5	Recommend the brand to others	1477	3.91	High
Average Brand Building (Y2)		1412.50	3.74	High
Reach and retain customers (Y3)				
SPD6	Expanding digital platform capabilities and features	1418	3.75	High
SPD7	Using social media platforms to absorb customer aspirations	1425	3.77	High
SPD8	Existing and having marketing campaigns	1512	4.00	High
Average Reach and retain customers (Y3)		1451.67	3.84	High
Average Digital Marketing Strategy		1429.83	3.78	High

Source: Processed data

Table 7: Marketing Performance of Management Level Employees at PT Pegadaian in DKI Jakarta (n=378)

Marketing Performance Indicators (KP)		Score	Average	Category
Sales Increase (Y4)				
KP1	Able to meet changing customer needs	1375	3.64	High
KP2	All products achieve brand equity status and superior performance	1265	3.35	High Enough
Average Sales Increase (Y4)		1320.00	3.49	High
Overall Business Growth (Y5)				
KP3	Achievement of market share percentage	1453	3.84	High
KP4	Achievement of significant value in business growth	1270	3.36	High Enough
Overall Business Growth Average (Y5)		1361.50	3.60	High
Average Marketing Performance		1340.75	3.55	High

Source: Processed data

Table 8: Suitability of Hybrid Measurement Model – SEM

Goodness of Fit Indicator	Expected Size	Estimation Results	Conclusion
Absolute Fit Size			
Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	GFI > 0,90	0,92	Good Fit
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	RMSEA < 0,08	0,075	Good Fit
Incremental Fit Size			
Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI)	NNFI > 0,90	0,95	Good Fit
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	NFI > 0,90	0,96	Good Fit
Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)	AGFI > 0,90	0,91	Good Fit
Relative Fit Index (RFI)	RFI > 0,90	0,94	Good Fit
Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	IFI > 0,90	0,97	Good Fit
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	CFI > 0,90	0,97	Good Fit

Source: Processed data

Table 9: Hybrid Model Measurement Analysis (Full Model)

Measurement Model		SLF	STD. Error (SE)	t-Value	Reliability Construct (CR)	Extract Variance (VE)
Latent Variables	Manifest Variables					
Market Oriented Organizational Culture (BOBP)	Customer satisfaction, (X1)	0.78	0.048	16.21	0.977	0.935
	Customer loyalty (X2)	0.76	0.043	17.87		
	Sustainable competitive advantage (X3)	0.86	0.044	19.70		
Organizational Capabilities (KO)	Human resources (X4)	0.83	0.043	19.30	0.978	0.938
	Technology (X5)	0.75	0.038	19.96		
	Process (X6)	0.85	0.050	16.90		
Management Innovation (IM)	Work methods (X7)	0.82	0.043	19.17	0.972	0.945
	Leadership approach (X8)	0.78	0.031	25.00		
Digital Marketing	Promoting products or services (Y1)	0.83	0.055	15.12	0.972	0.920

Measurement Model		SLF	STD. Error (SE)	t-Value	Reliability Construct (CR)	Extract Variance (VE)
Latent Variables	Manifest Variables					
Strategy (SPD)	Building a brand (Y2)	0.70	0.047	15.05		
	Reaching and retaining customers (Y3)	0.80	0.056	14.20		
Marketing Performance (KP)	Sales Increase (Y4)	0.75	0.044	17.24	0.964	0.931
	Overall Business Growth (Y5)	0.78	0.044	17.85		

Source: Processed data

Table 10: Summary of Latent Variable Inter-Test Results

No	Structural Path	Path Coefficient	t-Value	t- criteria	Test Results
1	Market Oriented Organizational Culture → Digital Marketing Strategy	0.36	5.75	1.96	Significant
2	Organizational Capabilities → Digital Marketing Strategy	0.31	4.10	1.96	Significant
3	Management Innovation → Digital Marketing Strategy	0.39	6.59	1.96	Significant
4	Market Oriented Organizational Culture → Kinerja Pemasaran	0.18	2.06	1.96	Significant
5	Organizational Capabilities → Kinerja Pemasaran	0.32	4.57	1.96	Significant
6	Management Innovation → Kinerja Pemasaran	0.21	2.76	1.96	Significant
7	Digital Marketing Strategy → Marketing Performance	0,45	8.97	1.96	Significant

Source: Processed data

Substructural Model 1

$$SPD = 0.36*BOBP + 0.31*KO + 0.39*IM, \text{ Errorvar.} = 0.30, R^2 = 0.70$$

(0.062)	(0.076)	(0.059)	(0.088)
5.75	4.10	6.59	6.29

Substructural Model 2

$$KP = 0.18*BOBP + 0.32*KO + 0.21*IM + 0.45*SPD, \text{ Errorvar.} = 0.15, R^2 = 0.85$$

(0.087)	(0.07)	(0.076)	(0.05)	(0.053)
2.06	4.57	2.76	8.97	3.97

Figure 2: Hybrid Model (Full SEM) Standardized

Figure 3: Hybrid Model (Full SEM) t-Value

Table 11: Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis		Hypothesis Statement	Path Coef./R ²	t value	t criteria	Test Results
H1	H ₀	Market-Oriented Organizational Culture has no effect on Digital Marketing Strategy	0.36	5.75	1.96	H ₀ is rejected and H _a is accepted. Market-Oriented Organizational Culture has an effect on Digital Marketing Strategy
	H _a	Market-Oriented Organizational Culture has an effect on Digital Marketing Strategy				
H2	H ₀	Organizational Capabilities has no Influence on Digital Marketing Strategy	0.31	4.10	1.96	H ₀ is rejected and H _a is accepted. Organizational Capability has a significant effect on Digital Marketing Strategy
	H _a	Organizational Capabilities has an Influence on Digital Marketing Strategy				
H3	H ₀	Management Innovation has no effect on Digital Marketing Strategy	0.39	6.59	1.96	H ₀ is rejected and H _a is accepted. Management Innovation has a significant influence on Digital Marketing Strategy
	H _a	Management Innovation has an effect on Digital Marketing Strategy				
H4	H ₀	Market-Oriented Organizational Culture has no effect on Marketing Performance	0.18	2.06	1.96	H ₀ is rejected and H _a is accepted. Market-Oriented Organizational Culture has a significant effect on Marketing Performance
	H _a	Market-Oriented Organizational Culture has an effect on Marketing Performance				
H5	H ₀	Organizational Capability has no effect on Marketing Performance	0.32	4.57	1.96	H ₀ is rejected and H _a is accepted. Organizational Capability has a significant effect on Marketing Performance
	H _a	Organizational Capability has an effect on Marketing Performance				
H6	H ₀	Management Innovation has no effect on Marketing Performance	0.21	2.76	1.96	H ₀ is rejected and H _a is accepted. Management Innovation has a significant effect on Marketing Performance
	H _a	Management Innovation has an effect on Marketing Performance				
H7	H ₀	Digital marketing strategy does not affect marketing performance	0.45	8.97	1.96	H ₀ is rejected and H _a is accepted. Digital Marketing Strategy has a significant effect on Marketing Performance
	H _a	Digital marketing strategy affects marketing performance				

Source: Processed data

- H₁: Market Oriented Organizational Culture has a significant effect on Digital Marketing Strategy.
- H₂: Organizational Capabilities has a significant effect on Digital Marketing Strategy.
- H₃: Management Innovation has a significant effect on Digital Marketing Strategy.
- H₄: Market Oriented Organizational Culture has a significant effect on Marketing Performance.
- H₅: Organizational Capabilities has a significant effect on Marketing Performance.
- H₆: Management Innovation has a significant effect on Marketing Performance.
- H₇: Digital Marketing Strategy has a significant effect on Marketing Performance.

V. CONCLUSION

Digital Marketing Strategy is a dominant variable on the Marketing Performance variable at PT Pegadaian, where the Digital Marketing Strategy variable successfully mediates explaining its influence on the research problem, namely Marketing Performance. In relation to exogenous and endogenous variables, all can explain their influence on endogenous variables with a positive correlation.

Bibliography

- 1) Allen, R. (2017). Marketing Communication Based on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty: Zantel Tanzania. *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*.
<https://doi.org/10.18178/ijimt.2017.8.4.742>
- 2) Amr Al-Ansi, Heesup Han*. 2019. *Role of halal-friendly destination performances, value, satisfaction, and trust in generating destination image and loyalty*. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management* 13 (2019) 51–60.
- 3) Apriliyanti, Syarifah Hidayah² dan Saida Zainurossalamia. (2020). *The influence of tourist attractions, destination image and tourist facilities on tourist satisfaction, the image of commerce as a center reflecting the unique culture of Samarinda City*. *Jurnal Manajemen - Vol. 12 (1) 2020*, 145-153 pISSN: 0285-6911 - eISSN: 2528-1518145
- 4) Artuger, S., Cetinsoz, B.C. & Kilic, I. (2013). The Effect of Destination Image on Destination Loyalty: An Application in Alanya. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(13), 124–136.
- 5) Battor, M., & Battour, M. (2013). Can organizational learning foster customer relationships? Implications for performance. *Learning Organization*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TLO-11-2012-0073>
- 6) Beerli, A., & Martín, J. D. (2004). Factors influencing destination image. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 31(3), 657–681. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2004.01.010>
- 7) Castro, A. & R. (2004). The Influence of Employee Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Customer Loyalty. *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, 15, 27
- 8) Charles Lagat and Gary L. Frankwick. (2017). Marketing capability, marketing strategy implementation and performance in small firms. *J. Global Business Advancement*, Vol. 10, No. 3, 2017

- 9) Chi, C. G. Q., & Qu, H. (2008). Examining the structural relationships of destination image, tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty: An integrated approach. *Tourism Management*, 29(4), 624–636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2007.06.007>
- 10) Chotivanich, P. (2014). Service Quality, Satisfaction, and Customer Loyalty in a Full-Service Domestic Airline in Thailand. *International Journal of Arts & Sciences*, 07(03), 161–169
- 11) Indra Muis. (2020). Marketing Strategy and Capability as the Mediators in Relationship of Market Orientation and Export Performance: A Case Study of Rattan Processing SMEs. *Binus Business Review*, 11(1), March 2020, 31-42 DOI: 10.21512/bbr.v11i1.5964
- 12) Limakrisna, Nandan dan Togi Parulian Purba. (2019). Marketing Management: Theory and Application in Business in Indonesia. Edition 3. Jakarta: Mitra Wacana Media.
- 13) Lucas Jorge Garcia, Galdenoro Botura Junior, João Carlos Riccó Plácido da Silva (2023). Innovation And Marketing Strategy: A Systematic Review *International Journal of Innovation - IJI*, São Paulo, 11(3), p. 1-24, e23150, Sept./Dec.
- 14) Rahman Khan, A., & Aminul Islam, M. (2017). The Impact of Digital Marketing On Increasing Customer Loyalty: A Study On Dhaka City, Bangladesh. In *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*.
- 15) Ri'aeni, I. (2017). LUGAS Jurnal Komunikasi ISSN 2580-8338 Volume I, Nomor 02, Desember 2017. *Komunikasi*, 1(02), 142–149.
- 16) Richard Allen Senguo, Sun Xixiang, and Nasero Charles Kilango *Marketing International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*, Vol. 8, No. 4, August 2017. doi:10.18178/ijimt.2017.8.4.742 284.
- 17) Souiden, N., Ladhari, R., & Chiadmi, N. E. (2017). Destination personality and destination image. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2017.04.003>
- 18) Stanley, A., & Chinelo, A. (2017). Wwww.Oaijse.Com Improving Customer Satisfaction Through Digital Marketing In The Nigerian Deposit Money Banks. *Certified ISSN (Online)*.
- 19) Williams Kwasi Peprah, Evans O. N. D. Ocansey, Emmanuel Kofi Mintah. (2017), The Influence of Culture on Global Marketing Strategies: A Confirmatory Study. *The International Journal of Business & Management (ISSN 2321–8916) www.theijbm.com*.
- 20) Indra Muis. (2020). Marketing Strategy and Capability as the Mediators in Relationship of Market Orientation and Export Performance: A Case Study of Rattan Processing SMEs. *Binus Business Review*, 11(1), March 2020, 31-42 DOI: 10.21512/bbr.v11i1.5964